

STUDIES ON RANCIDITY OF BUTTERFAT. PART VI

THE ACTION OF LIGHT

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Butterfat, exposed to diffused light, light from a tungsten filament lamp, ultraviolet light and X-rays, develops rancidity in presence of oxygen, the rate of development of rancidity being proportional to the intensity of the exciting source. In complete absence of oxygen even X-rays and ultraviolet light are ineffective in producing off-flavour. Only the lower saturated acids, C_4 and C_6 , are oxidised by the action of light, the higher members remaining unaffected.

It has long been known that fats and fat containing food materials exposed to sunlight develop an unpleasant odour and flavour much more rapidly than when preserved in the dark. Ritsert (*Natures. Wchenschhr.*, 331, 343) observed that exposure to light had a remarkable effect in accelerating the development of rancidity. But subsequent reports show a great deal of confusion regarding the part played by light, some asserting that light and oxygen are both essential for the onset of rancidity, while others claim that light alone in absence of oxygen is capable of producing rancidity (Wagner *et al.*, *Z. natur. Nahr. Genussm.*, 1913, 25, 704). Schmalfuss and collaborators (*Marg. Ind.*, 1935, 25, 215) have shown that saturated and unsaturated fatty acids and glycerides give rise to small amounts of odorous aldehydes and ketones when subjected to prolonged heating or exposed to ultraviolet light. These workers assert that oxygen and moisture are not essential but assist the reaction and that ketones and acids are produced during irradiation more easily from those containing 12 or fewer carbon atoms than from C_{14} , C_{16} and C_{18} acids. It is a common knowledge that ultraviolet light is very effective in accelerating the deterioration of fats. It has been shown by Lea (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, 108, B, 175) that a fat exposed at a constant room temperature to the light from an electric lamp oxidises much more rapidly than a control sample in the dark, in spite of the fact that the ultraviolet component of the radiation from the electric lamp filament is very small.

Comparatively little work has been done on the quantitative relationship between rancidity and intensity of illumination. Rogers and Taylor (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 1334) studied the absorption of oxygen by linseed oil under ultraviolet irradiation and were able to show that the spoilage, which was negligible in the absence of light, was not directly proportional to the intensity of illumination, but that weaker the light employed, the greater was the efficiency in producing rancidity.

It has already been shown (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 239) that the role of light is one of positive catalyst and that samples of butterfat stored in diffused day light in the absence of oxygen fail to produce any organoleptic rancidity for the period studied. It may generally be accepted that the action of light consists in

accelerating rancidity and that irradiation in complete absence of oxygen is incapable of producing rancidity. The fact that apparently sweet fats sometimes become rancid when exposed to light, out of contact with air, has been explained by Lea (*loc. cit.*) as due to the presence in the fat of minute amounts of oxygen either in solution or in loose chemical combination with unsaturated acids. This oxygen under the influence of strong light may be quite sufficient to affect the flavour of fats.

With an idea to elucidating this point further, a detailed study has been made of the effect of light both in presence of oxygen as also in the complete absence of it, using different sources of illumination as the exciting agency, viz. sunlight, electric light from tungsten filament lamp, ultraviolet light from mercury vapour lamp and finally X-rays.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Effect of Storage of Butterfat in Dark after Exposure to a 100-watt lamp for different Periods.—Butterfat was placed in small petri dishes (3" diam.) and was irradiated for 1, 3, 5, 8, 10, 12 and 15 hours by light from a 100-watt tungsten filament lamp, the samples being kept at a distance of 15 cm. from the exciting source. After the desired period each sample was transferred to darkness at 37°. The development of rancidity was followed by the determination of the peroxide value and the results are tabulated below.

TABLE I

Expt. No.	Exposure.	Peroxide value after days.					
		10.	15.	20.	30.	40.	50.
1	1 hr.	0.25	0.35	0.40	0.55	0.75	1.05
2	3	0.25	0.35	0.45	0.60	0.85	1.20
3	5	0.25	0.50	0.55	0.70	0.90	1.25
4	8	0.25	0.50	0.60	0.85	1.1	1.40
5	10	0.25	0.50	0.68	1.0	1.3	1.60
6	12	0.25	0.50	0.70	—	1.58	2.0
7	15	0.25	0.55	0.80	1.40	2.0	2.5
8	Control sample	0.0	0.05	0.20	0.30	0.55	0.80

Samples 1 and 2 developed slightly off-flavour. This was more pronounced in the case of samples 3-5. Samples 6 and 7 were distinctly rancid both organoleptically as well as from peroxide % determinations. The control sample did not develop organoleptic rancidity until at the end of 60 days, when distinct signs of such rancidity could be detected.

It is evident from Table I that exposure to light of relatively low intensity even for a limited period can have a very pronounced effect on the development of oxidative rancidity on subsequent storage in darkness. The results are graphically shown in Figure 1 where oxidation can be seen to proceed in the absence of light at a rate depending probably on the amount of energy absorbed

FIG. 1

during the short exposure to light. From these results at least one thing appears certain that the increased oxidation in irradiated samples may be ascribed to the action of light, for under the experimental conditions the control unexposed sample did not develop detectable rancidity even at the end of one and a half month. Lea (*loc. cit.*) has studied a similar effect with a beef-kidney fat, and the present results are fully in agreement with those observed by him.

Effect of Light Intensity.—For this purpose, samples of butterfat were irradiated as before for a definite period (12 hours) at different distances from the exciting source (100-watt W-lamp) viz., 15 cm., 20 cm., 30 cm. and 60 cm. and the samples subsequently kept at atmospheric conditions at a temperature of 37° in an incubator. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Distance from lamp.	Peroxide value after days.			
	15.	20.	30.	45.
Control (unexposed)	0.14	0.30	0.40	2.4
15 cm.	0.60	1.00	3.7	5.9
20	0.60	1.00	3.5	5.0
30	0.40	0.82	3.0	4.0
60	0.30	0.50	2.4	3.0

It is evident from the above table that increasing the distance of the source of light from the fat *i.e.* decreasing the intensity of light, is also accompanied by a decrease in the development of peroxide value of fats, and it will not be wrong to conclude that the relation between the rate of oxidation and intensity of irradiation may be one of direct proportionality. Rogers and Taylor (*loc. cit.*), however, observed that in the oxidation of linseed oil, weaker the light employed, greater was the oxidation.

Effect of Storage of Butterfat in Air on the Development of Rancidity after Exposure to Ultraviolet Light for different Periods.—Samples of butterfat (50 c. c. each) were exposed to the action of ultraviolet light from a mercury vapour lamp in small dishes for 2, 5, 10, 15, 25, 35, 45 and 75 minutes respectively and after this period, the samples were removed to small open glass jars and kept stored in an incubator at 37.5°, after immediately determining the peroxide value of the fat samples. These were then analysed at suitable intervals and the experimental results are given in the table below.

TABLE III

Both oxygen and moisture present ; storage temperature = 37.5°.

Expt. No.	Time of exposure.	Peroxide value					
		Original.	Immediately after exposure.	After 15 days.	After 30 days.	After 60 days.	After 90 days.
1	2 min.	0.56	0.86	2.7	6.8	11.5	35.4
2	5	0.56	1.0	3.0	7.2	18.7	40.1
3	10	0.56	1.0	3.6	8.0	24.1	42.3
4	15	0.56	1.30	3.8	8.1	31.4	49.5
5	25	0.56	1.30	3.9	8.1	31.1	52.0
6	35	0.56	1.45	4.0	8.0	39.0	59.2
7	45	0.56	1.72	5.3	10.0	42.5	60.6
8	75	0.56	2.10	5.6	15.0	49.5	70.0
9	Control	0.56	—	0.70	0.88	3.65	9.2

It will be clear from the above table that exposure of fats to ultraviolet light reduces the induction period considerably, pronounced rancidity being detectable at the end of 10 to 15 days. In samples 7 and 8, irradiated respectively for 45 and 75 minutes, the fats oxidised without induction period, off-flavours being detectable immediately after the exposure. The experimental results are shown graphically in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2

Ultraviolet Irradiation and Rancidity in Presence and Absence of Oxygen.— So far the behaviour of light was studied in presence of a mospheric oxygen and pronounced oxidation was observed. In this section experiments were carried out to illustrate the function of light and oxygen on the development of rancidity. Ultraviolet light from a mercury vapour lamp was employed as the exciting source and samples of butterfat were irradiated at a distance of 15 cm. from the source in quartz vessels both in the presence and absence of oxygen. Complete absence of oxygen was effected by evacuation by means of

a diffusion pump for one hour only. Estimation of dissolved oxygen in the Van Slyke apparatus from a duplicate sample, evacuated for the same period, indicated completeness of the removal of oxygen. The time of exposure was 1, 2 and 24 hours.

TABLE IVA

Expt. No.	Condition of expt.	Time of exposure.	Values immediately after exposure		Organoleptic test.
			P.V.	Kreis.	
1	Oxygen present	1 hr.	0.86	2.2	Rancid, bad.
2	Do	2	0.90	2.6	" "
3	Do	24	4.50	10.0	Offensive
4	Oxygen absent	1	0.26	0.1	Practically unaltered
5	Do	2	0.28	0.1	Do
6	Do	24	0.26	0.1	Do
7	Control	...	0.26	0.1	Do

TABLE IVB

Development of rancidity in the irradiated samples (Table IVA) when exposed to atmospheric conditions.

Storage temperature = 37.5°.

Expt. No.	After 30 days.		After 60 days.		After 75 days.	
	P.V.	Kreis.	P.V.	Kreis.	P.V.	Kreis.
1	10.3	9.3	35.6	15.0	70.0	35.0
2	13.3	10.8	42.6	16.3	86.0	37.0
3	20.0	16.5	52.5	31.6	96.0	92.0
4	1.56	2.1	3.0	3.9	6.0	8.5
5	1.60	—	3.1	4.0	5.8	8.4
6	1.57	2.2	3.2	4.0	5.9	9.0
7	1.48	2.1	3.0	4.2	5.78	8.8

TABLE IVC

Development of peroxide and Kreis values after 75 days in the samples irradiated in vacuum and stored as such.

Hours of exposure.	After 75 days.		Organoleptic test.
	P.V.	Kreis.	
1	0.20	0.8	Smell unaltered
2	0.30	1.0	Do
24	0.30	1.2	Do
Control in air	5.78	8.8	Highly rancid
Control in vacuum	0.20	0.8	Not rancid

It will be evident from these tables that whereas exposure in presence of oxygen can produce off-flavour almost immediately after the exposure, the

smell remains unaltered after the period of exposure in absence of oxygen. Storage of the samples exposed subsequently to atmospheric conditions developed pronounced rancidity in samples 1, 2 and 3, where oxygen was present during irradiation, whereas samples 4, 5 and 6, irradiated in absence of oxygen oxidised very nearly at the same rate as the unexposed control sample (Table IVB). Duplicate samples exposed in complete absence of oxygen did not develop rancidity when stored as such even after the period mentioned

FIG. 3

(Table IVc). Fig. 3 shows the behaviour of samples irradiated in ultraviolet in the development of rancidity in the presence and absence of O_2 .

Effect of X-ray Irradiation on the Development of Rancidity of Butterfat.—

The experimental evidences assembled in the previous section clearly indicate that the part played by light consists definitely in accelerating the rate of autoxidation of fats by atmospheric oxygen and that rancidity cannot develop in the absence of oxygen even under the influence of ultraviolet irradiation. In this section the effect of X-rays, a more powerful source of radiant energy, has been used in the irradiation of fat and its effect on the development of rancidity has been studied in the presence and absence of oxygen. Thunberg's tubes were used for experiments conducted in absence of oxygen and the samples were exposed to the action of X-rays (wave-length 2 \AA) for different periods of time, viz. 10 minutes, 15 minutes and 1 hour. The results in Table V show that exposure in the presence of oxygen for

10 minutes (No. 1) is sufficient to develop pronounced rancidity in butterfat, whereas the samples 2 to 4, which were irradiated in the absence of oxygen,

FIG. 4

oxidised as slowly as the control samples which had not been subjected to irradiation. This relationship is clearly shown in Fig. 4.

TABLE V

Butterfat stored at 37.5°.

Expt. No.	Condition of the experiment (moisture, 0.2%)	Original.	Immediately after exposure.	Peroxide value.		
				After 10 days.	After 30 days.	After 60 days.
1.	10 minutes' exposure in presence of oxygen	0.30	0.56	4.36	1.30	29.5
2.	10 minutes' exposure in vacuum and than kept exposed to atmospheric conditions	0.30	0.30	0.45	1.64	3.2
3.	15 minutes' exposure in vacuum and then exposed to atmospheric conditions.	0.30	0.30	0.40	1.54	3.3
4.	1 hour's exposure in vacuum and kept exposed to atmosphere	0.30	0.30	0.40	1.38	3.0
5.	15 minutes' exposure in vacuum and stored as such	0.30	—	—	—	0.52
6.	Control in light	0.30	—	—	1.48	3.0

These experiments strongly favour the view that oxygen is primarily essential for the onset of rancidity. Sample No. 5 stored in vacuum after 15 minutes' exposure to the X-ray irradiation practically underwent no change organoleptically, an observation which has also been made with the ultraviolet irradiation experiments in the previous section.

Action of Light on the Oxidation of Saturated and Unsaturated Fatty Acids.—The action of light has thus definitely been shown to consist in accelerating the rate of development of rancidity in fats and it is generally believed to affect the oxidation of the unsaturated constituents of the glyceride molecules. The possibility of decomposition of saturated fatty acid chain should not, however, be overlooked, particularly after the experiments of Schmalfuss *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) and hence it was considered necessary to study the behaviour of light on the oxidation of both the saturated and unsaturated fatty acids and their glycerides. All the saturated acids from butyric to stearic, and oleic and linoleic acids among the unsaturated acids were employed in this study; of the glycerides only tributyrin, tristearin and triolein were used. Ultraviolet light was used as the source of light in view of its pronounced accelerating effect, already observed. Ultraviolet irradiation in quartz test tubes for a period of 30 minutes was normally employed. In order to prevent any volatile products of oxidation escaping to the atmosphere, the quartz tubes were connected with short delivery tubes dipping under a small volume of water contained in a test tube. The oxidised acids or the glycerides as also the water containing any absorbed product of oxidation were subjected to tests for aldehydes by Schiff's reagent, peroxide test with KI and acetic acid and for ketones by salicylaldehyde reaction of Tafel and Thaler (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1932, I, 265). The following table summarises the results.

TABLE VI

Effect of ultraviolet irradiation on fatty acid oxidation.

	Peroxide test.	Schiff's test.	Salicylaldehyde reaction.
Butyric acid	—	+	—
Caproic acid	—	Very feeble	—
C ₈ —C ₁₈ acids (saturated)	—	—	—
Oleic acid	+	+	—
Linoleic acid	+	+	—
Tributyrin	—	+	—
Tristearin	—	—	—
Triolein	+	+	—

Even prolonged irradiation for 12 hours failed to develop aldehyde or ketonic substances with higher saturated acids. These results indicate that

the saturated fatty acids are not normally affected during the oxidation, and the action of light consists mainly in producing accelerated oxidation of the unsaturated glycerides only, with the formation of peroxidic compounds.

C O N C L U S I O N

From the experiments enumerated above it is clear that light alone cannot be an initial starter of the rancidity in fats. As all these experiments have been conducted with samples, whose moisture content is 0.2%, one can also conclude with certainty that rancidity can be developed in the presence of oxygen alone, that light or moisture alone without oxygen cannot under any circumstances produce rancidity in fats. All previous observations, viz. Wagner *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) and Schmalzfuss *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) upholding exposure to light as capable of producing rancidity in vacuo, and those of Godbole and Sadgopal (*Z. untersuch Lebensmittel.*, 1936, 72, 35) claiming moisture as the fundamental cause of rancidity must therefore be erroneous. It has, however, been demonstrated in this paper that light plays a prominent role in producing accelerated rancidity in fats. Even exposure to weak artificial light is capable of decreasing the induction period of fats and can produce marked acceleration in the rate of subsequent oxidation, a conclusion already reached by Lea (*loc. cit.*). It is also clear that once a fat has been exposed to light rays so as to start oxidation at a sufficient rate, it cannot be stopped by removal of the exciting source. The nature and intensity of light also play a prominent role, ultraviolet light being more destructive than ordinary light and X-rays still more predominant in causing rancidity. From the results obtained, it may be concluded that at temperatures sufficiently low for thermal reactions to be negligible, fats exposed to strong illumination with free access of oxygen oxidise with little or no induction period at a rate which is roughly proportional to the intensity of light. The action of light consists essentially in accelerating the rate of oxidation of the unsaturated components of fats, but the lower saturated acids may be affected to a slight extent. Thus, exposure to light, though of undoubted importance, is only one of the factors which influence the development of oxidative rancidity.

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